

CRYSTAL AND MOLECULAR STRUCTURE OF THE U(VI) DIOXOCOMPLEX
WITH BENZOYLHYDROZONE OF SALICYLIC ALDEHYDE

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Gulbayev Yahshilik Irsalievich

Candidate of Chemical Sciences,

Department of Chemistry

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute

Assistant. **Abdullaev Alisher Abulkasimovich**

Department of Chemistry

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute

Assistant. **Buriboev Aziz Abdumanonovich**

Department of Chemistry

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute

Norkhujayeva Diyora Bakhtiyar daughter

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute 315-21 Group student

Annotation. *The molecular crystal and electronic structures of nitratamidinohydrazonacetone and thiosemicarbazone o-hydroxyacetophenone molecules were determined by X-ray diffraction and quantum chemical analyses. The reactivity of ligands is shown. In the structure of the U(VI) dioxocomplex with benzoyl hydrazone of salicylic aldehyde, the complex consists of a pentagonal-bipyramidal polyhedron, at the vertices of which are located multi-linked oxygen atoms of the uranyl group.*

Keywords: *Ligand, single crystal, X-ray structure, uranium, acylhydrazone, benzene hydrazone, salicylaldehyde*

Continuing the systematic study of the composition structure and properties of dioxocomplexes Mo(VI) and U (VI) with acylhydrazones of salicylic aldehyde(1.3), we studied the crystal structure of benzoyl hydrazone of salicylic aldehyde by the PCA method. This compound is the first crystalline product of U(VI) with the above compounds, it is obtained by dissolving a uranium dioxocomplex with benzoyl hydrazone of salicylic aldehyde in hot acetic acid, followed by holding the solution at room temperature for three days. The composition of the formed brown crystals was established in the process of determining the crystal structure.

Diffraction analysis. Single crystals with linear dimensions of 0.35 05 05 mm belong to a triclinic syngony with unit cell parameters: $a = 7,780$ (2), $b = c = \alpha = 109,81$ (5), $\beta = 104.60$ $\gamma = 86.46$ (5), etc. gr. P1, Z=2 Experimental material was obtained on an automatic diffractometer "Sintex P21" SuK radiation, graphite monochromator, $\theta/2\theta$ scanning, 2θ max = 1200). The complete set of experimental data for the calculation of the crystal structure consists of 2615 reflections $I \geq 2\sigma$ (1). Experimental accounting of absorption in the sample was carried out by azimuthal scanning of four reflections. All calculations for the X-ray diffraction study were performed on an IBM PC/AT personal computer. The structure was deciphered by the heavy atom method using the SHELX-76 SHELXS-86 software package (4). The coordinates of the hydrogen atoms were determined by calculation from the standard values of bond lengths and valence angles at C and N atoms for sp^2 hybridization. Refinement of the structure of the MNC with an anisotropic approximation was carried out to the value $R = 0.048$. The coordinates of the atoms, bond lengths, valence angles and deviations of the atoms from the RMS are given in Tables 1-4.

Table 1

Coordinates of atoms

Атом	X	Y	Z
U	0.1829(1)	0.2644(1)	0.4581(0)
O1U	0.0270(16)	0.2551(16)	0.5363(11)
O2U	0.3401(17)	0.2750(13)	0.3792(11)
O1A	0.2234(18)	0.5051(12)	0.5642(11)
O2A	0.0405(22)	0.6405(16)	0.6624(12)
C1A	0.1876(27)	0.5846(18)	0.6579(14)
C2A	0.3261(38)	0.6161(32)	0.7721(21)
O1	0.0407(20)	0.0727(12)	0.2837(10)
O2	0.4060(16)	0.2590(11)	0.6083(11)
N1	0.2326(20)	0.066(14)	0.4586(12)
N2	0.1514(18)	0.0973(14)	0.3550(12)
C1	0.4463(23)	0.1945(18)	0.6894(14)
C2	0.5434(29)	0.2680(20)	0.856(17)
C3	0.5873(28)	0.2096(22)	0.8909(15)
C4	0.5306(33)	0.0671(25)	0.8608(17)
C5	0.4395(28)	0.0088(20)	0.7508(15)
C6	0.3961(24)	0.0505(17)	0.6635(14)

C7	0.3074(22)	0.0369(18)	0.5470(15)
C8	0.0520(25)	0.0551(18)	0.2692(15)
C9	0.0320(24)	0.1599(18)	0.1583(14)
C10	0.0727(27)	0.2959(19)	0.1447(16)
C11	0.1536(29)	0.3870(20)	0.0382(19)
C12	0.1900(31)	0.3547(22)	0.0604(19)
C13	0.1441(34)	0.2140(23)	0.0526(20)
C14	0.0803(35)	0.1234(21)	0.0607(16)
O1W	0.2617(18)	0.3815(12)	0.3505(12)

Table 2
Link lengths

Connection	d, Å	Connection	d, Å
U-O1U	1,76(1)	C1-C6	1,44 (2)
U-O2U	1,78 (1)	C6-C7	1,43 (2)
U-OA1	2,34 (1)	C7-N1	1,31 (2)
U-OA2	2,38 (1)	N1-N2	1,38 (1)
U-O1	2,43 (1)	N2-N8	1,33 (2)
U-O2	2,22 (1)	C8-O1	1,25 (2)
U-N1	2,62 (1)	C8-O1	1,44 (2)
O2-C1	1,34 (1)	C8-C9	1,39 (2)
C1-C2	1,41 (2)	C9-C10	1,38 (2)
C2-C3	1,34 (2)	C10-C11	1,33 (3)
C3-C4	1,43 (2)	C11-C12	1,46 (3)
C4-C5	1,35 (2)	C12-C13	1,38 (2)
C5-C6	1,34 (2)	C14-C9	1,34 (3)

Table 3
Valence angles, deg.

Corner	Hail.	Corner	Hail.
O1UO2U	180 (1)	C5 C6 C1	119 (1)
O1U U O2	91 (1)	C6 C1 C2	117 (1)
O1U U N1	99 (1)	O2 C1 C6	123 (1)
O1 U U O1	93 (1)	C1 C6 C7	122 (1)
O1U U O A1	89 (1)	C7 C6 C5	118 (1)
O1 U U OA2	89 (1)	C6 C7 N1	126 (1)

O2 U N1	70 (1)	C7 N1 U1	129 (1)
O2 U O2U	89 (1)	U1 N1 N2	
O2 U O1	129 (1)	N2 N1 C7	115 (1)
O2 U OA1	80 (1)	N1 N2 C8	117 (1)
N1 U O2U	90 (1)	N2 C8 O1	120 (1)
N1 U O1	61 (1)	U1 O1 C8	127 (1)
N1 U OA1	148 (1)	O1 C8 C9	122 (1)
O2U U O1	87 (1)	C8 C9 C10	123 (1)
O2U U OA1	90 (1)	C10 C11	124 (1)
		C12	
O1 U OA1	150 (1)	C11 C 12	119 (1)
		C13	
U1 O2 C1	139 (1)	C12 C13	115 (1)
		C14	
O2 C1 C2	120 (1)	C13 C14 C9	126 (1)
C1 C2 C3	122 (1)	C14 C9 C10	119 (1)
C2 C3 C4	117 (1)	C14 C9 C8	119 (1)
C3 C4 C5	122 (1)		(1)
C4 C5 C6	120 (2)		(1)

Table 4

Deviation of atoms (Å) from the RMS planes of individual fragments of molecules in the structure

Plane	Atoms					
I	C	C	C	C	C	C
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	-	-	0.00	-	-	-
	0.007	0,001	6	0.005	0.004	0.009
II	O	C	C	C	N	U*
	(2)	(1)	(6)	(7)	(1)	
	0.00	-	0,00	0,01	-	-
	1	0,16	7		0,01	0,21
III	O	C	N	N	U	
	(1)	(8)	(2)	(1)		
	0.00	-	0.02	-	0.00	
	1	0.014	4	0.018	6	

IV	C (9)	C (10)	C (11)	C (12)	C (13)	C (14)
	0,02	0.00	-	-	0.04	-
	9	1	0.002	0.018	5	0.054

It can be seen from Fig. 1 that the complex consists of a pentagonally bipyramidal polyhedron, at the vertices of which are multi-linked oxygen atoms of the uranyl group.

Fig. 1. Packing of complex U(VI) molecules in the structure.

The angle between the axial oxygen atoms O1UO2U is equal to 179.6 (1), which indicates their linearity. The bond lengths are 1-G 1.76 (2) and O2-G 1.78 (2) Å, they are almost equal-shouldered and directed perpendicular to the equatorial plane of uranium.

Pentacoordination of the uranyl ion is carried out by monodeprotonated tridentate benzoyl hydrazone of salicylic aldehyde and one oxygen atom each of the carboxylate groups of two acetic acid anions.

Fig. 2. General view of the molecule.

The coordination of the carboxylate anion occurs by type a-2-c (3).

USED LITERATURE

1. Gulbaev J. I. et al. Crystal and molecular structure of uranium dioxocomplex with benzoyl hydezone of salicylic aldehyde //UZBEKSKII KHIMICHESKII ZHURNAL. – 1997. – С. 28-31.
2. Гулбоев Я. И., Исомиддинов Ж. КРИСТАЛЛИЧЕСКАЯ И МОЛЕКУЛЯРНАЯ СТРУКТУРА ДИМЕРА УРАНА //Журнал естественных наук. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 2.
3. Gulbayev Y. I. et al. Benzoilgidrozon solitsiloviy aldegidni infraqizil spektroskopiya yordamida aniqlash //Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 163-168.
4. Шарипов Х. Т. и др. КРИСТАЛЛИЧЕСКАЯ И МОЛЕКУЛЯРНАЯ СТРУКТУРА ДИОКСОКОМПЛЕКСА U (VI) С БЕНЗООИЛГИДРОЗОНОМ САЛИЦИЛОВОГО АЛЬДЕГИДА //Scientific progress. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 330-339.
5. Абдуллаев А. А. Олмалик кон-металлургия комбинатидаги молибден сақлаган кекларини қайта ишлаш жараёни //Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 225-228.
6. Гулбоев Я. И., Исомиддинов Ж. КРИСТАЛЛИЧЕСКАЯ И МОЛЕКУЛЯРНАЯ СТРУКТУРА ДИМЕРА УРАНА //Журнал естественных наук. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 2.
7. Gulbaev J. I. et al. Synthesis and crystalline structure of thiosemicarbasons and o-oxy-acetophenon //UZBEKSKII KHIMICHESKII ZHURNAL. – 1997. – С. 43-44.

